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VALERIA

Validation of low-voltage energy and renewables integration analysis

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Executive Summary

Integration of high shares of renewable energy sources into the energy systems is one of today's major challenges. The startup elena international and the Potsdam-Institute for Climate Impact Research have developed an open-source library for transient stability analysis. In order to further develop the software, the simulation results were compared with measured data in the Smart Grid Technologies Laboratory at TECNALIA. The focus was on the modelling of lines, grid-following and grid-forming inverters as well as the comparison between grid-connected and islanded modes. The whole open-source community will benefit from the tests conducted since a validated open-source library can build the basis for further research projects and practice.

1. General Information of the User Project

The title of the user project is validation of low-voltage energy and renewables integration analysis with the acronym "VALERIA". The host infrastructure was the Smart Grid Technologies Laboratory at TECNALIA. The access period was from January 20th until January 31st 2020. The user group members attending were Christina Vogel and Dr. Sabine Auer from elena international GmbH as well as Tobias Deß, Anton Plietzsch and Raphael Kogler from the Potsdam-Institute of Climate Impact Research.

2. Research Motivation

The EU has set a binding renewable energy target for 2030 of at least 32% with a clause for a possible upward revision by 2023 in the revised Renewables energy directive (2018/2001). In order to meet this goal without risking grid stability problems and reliability of supply, numerous technological challenges have to be met. One important aspect here is that a majority of renewable energies are connected to the grid with inverters. Another fact is that 90% of all renewable energy plants are connected to the mid- and low voltage grid. These changes in structure and dynamic of power grids ask for new ways of control which have to be modeled and validated in order to ensure a safe and efficient grid operation in the future. During the CoNDyNet project funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, world-class power system research with over 60 peer-reviewed publications has been conducted. Drawing from the results of this research, during a Pathfinder and Accelerator programme of Climate-KIC, the EU's main climate innovation initiative, we developed the open-source library *PowerDynamics.jl*¹. This software is doing transient stability analysis and is being co-developed by the Potsdam-Institute of Climate Impact Research (PIK) and the start-up elena (electricity network analysis) international which is a spin-off from PIK. Now, the analysis of *PowerDynamics.jl* was validated against testbed data during the EriGrid project. The outcome were concrete steps for improvement of the open-source software for transient stability analysis which can be used by both researchers and practitioners. In contrast, closed-source software cannot be used by research since there are calculations and models the researcher cannot evaluate because they are not open and available to her/him. So far, there is no open-source software and no publicly validated software that has this functionality.

2.1. Objectives

Dynamic stability analysis has been identified as one of the fundamental issues with increasing renewable energy penetration [3]. To tackle this issue, elena international GmbH and the Potsdam-Institute of Climate Impact Research developed the open source library *PowerDynamics.jl*. It was presented during the openmod conference 2018 as well as the Wind Integration Workshop 2018. During our stay in the Tecnalia testbed, we aimed at validating this open-source library. The experiments conducted and results are presented in the following.

¹<https://github.com/JuliaEnergy/PowerDynamics.jl>

Scenario	Test Case	Description
test case 1: base test case with a slack node and a load		
1.1	1	sudden loss of load
1.3	1	sudden loss of load, difference in line resistance
1.5	1	reactive power increase
test case 2: setup with a slack node, a line, a load and a grid-forming inverter		
2.3	2	setpoint dispatch at voltage source inverter
test case 2a: variation of test case 2 without the slack node		
2a.2	2a	large load increase
2a.3	2a	setpoint dispatch at voltage source inverter
test case 2b: variation of test case 2 with a different line connection		
2b.2	2b	large load increase
2b.3	2b	setpoint dispatch at voltage source inverter
2b.4	2b	dispatch at current source inverter
Test Case 3b: setup with a slack bus, a load, a grid-forming inverter and a grid-following inverter with a solar plant		
3b.2	3b	large load increase
3b.4	3b	dispatch at current source inverter
3b.5	3b	line opening
Test Case 5: setup with a pacific power source, a load and a grid-forming inverter		
5.1x	5	frequency changes at the slack node with different slopes
5.2x	5	change in voltage amplitude at the slack node
Test Case 6: setup pacific power source, load and grid-following inverter		
6.1x	6	frequency change at the slack with different slopes
6.2x	6	change in voltage amplitude at the slack node

Table 1.: Overview of the test cases and fault scenarios conducted.

2.2. Scope

We conducted fault scenarios with six different testcase setups, that is six different grid topologies. For some of the setups, different variations were used (indicated with "a" and "b"). For each testcase, a couple of fault scenarios was performed. For this report, only the most interesting setups and scenarios have been selected (see table 1). For a validation with *PowerDynamics.jl*, we choose the scenarios 2b.2 and 2b.3. First, the measurement data had to be post-processed so that it can be compared to the simulation (see section 5.1). Then, for each of the two scenarios, the components were modeled in the software and fault scenarios were simulated (see section 5.2).

3. State-of-the-Art/State-of-Technology

In conventional energy systems, grid dynamics are mainly determined by synchronous machines [5]. Their dynamic behaviour and control is thus well researched and classified [8, 5]. For most renewable energy plants and storages, inverters are interfacing the grid. [8, 12]. For the future energy systems based on renewable energy, these components have to be modeled correctly for design, analysis and control. For dynamic behaviour, especially time frames in the second up to minute scale are of interest [8]. In our research, we found that control schemes of inverters may cause instabilities if poorly designed, e.g. reaction delays of grid-following inverters or smart meters [10]. This was acknowledged by the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E) one year later in their guidance document [3]. This raises the need to study Delayed Differential Equations (DDEs) to suggest adequate control solutions [11]. One part of our expertise lies in explicitly modeling DDEs. Power grids are high-dimensional non-linear systems. Since simulations of power system dynamics are computationally very demanding usually, their full time-domain analysis is simplified by linearizing the dynamics and investigating small perturbations only. In our research we have undertaken time-domain analysis for transient stability, taking into account the system's full non-linearity and taming its high-dimensionality with novel sampling-based approaches [7, 6, 4, 2]. The required sample size does not depend on the system's dimension, in contrast to conventional methods where it grows exponentially. Hence, it is part of our innovation to provide a reliable stability analysis even against practically very relevant large perturbations, e.g. due to the sudden loss of load or generation, line tripping etc. For the dynamic simulation of power grids (transient analysis), there is a number of elaborated commercial software tools like PSSE, PowerFactory, Matlab Simulink etc. However, models of inverters are black-box models and do not allow for a transparent validation of modelling results and thus no quick transfer of latest research results. Since different types of inverters and manufacturer's models are written in different software and in different degrees of complexity, it is impossible to harmonize them in a common simulation model. At the same time, the energy transition demands for a fast development and continuous improvement of reliable simulation tools for dynamic grid analysis [1]. Thus, open source solutions are an important contribution for a grid-stable energy transformation. For dynamic modelling of frequency and voltage stability as well as for modeling synchronization behaviour in the second and sub-second domain, there was no open source library available. In September 2018, we released a first version of *PowerDynamics.jl* (GNU General Public License v3.0) in order to fill this gap and we are since then developing it further. With the usage of Julia as a high-performance programming language we allow for incorporating novel features from the dynamics of renewable energy and power electronics by making use of cutting-edge solvers [9] for

DAE (Differential Algebraic Equations), SDAE (Stochastic Differential Algebraic Equations) and DDEs for incorporating algebraic constraints of loads, the stochasticity of renewable energy and delays from power electronics. In order to build up *PowerDynamics.jl* as a sound basis for further research and practice, we planned to validate it with three test cases during the ERIGrid Project VALERIA. For practical application of the research, elena international is offering an analysis service based on *PowerDynamics.jl*. This service enables grid operators and utilities to increase the share of renewables cost-efficiently without harming frequency or voltage constraints.

4. Executed Tests and Experiments

4.1. Components

In the following, an overview of the components used in the experiment setups is given.

4.1.1. Interconnection to the Spanish grid

The Smart Grid Technologies Laboratory at TECNALIA has a connection to the Spanish power grid which allows for the synchronization of the inverters with a real power grid in operation. In the simulation in *PowerDynamics.jl*, this connection is modeled as a slack node. During the experiments we found the AC signal from the grid to introduce a lot of noise.

4.1.2. Pacific power source

Instead of the connection to the Spanish grid, the pacific power source can be used to feed power into the test system. As long as the pacific power source is feeding power into the system ($P_{slack} \geq 0$) it behaves like a slack bus and can be modeled as such. The AC signal of the pacific power source proved to introduce a lot less noise compared to the connection to the Spanish power grid. Taking the pacific power source as a slack bus further allowed for a fault scenario where the voltage amplitude and frequency at the slack bus are changed.

4.1.3. Loads

The loads in the laboratory consist of ohmic resistances and inductive reactances which can be changed stepwise. In most of the test cases, we use purely resistive loads which have no inductive part.

4.1.4. Current source inverter (grid-following mode)

In the smart grid laboratory, there were two custom-built inverters. Both of them can be run in either grid-following mode as a current source inverter (CSI), or in grid-forming mode as a voltage source inverter (VSI). The current source inverter sets the voltage angle frequency with a phase-locked-loop (PLL). The power output is regulated by a droop control.

Equations of the current source inverter The inverter control is implemented in the dq -reference-frame:

$$\vec{V}_{dq,meas} = e^{-j\theta} \vec{V}_{\alpha\beta,meas}$$

The measured voltage signal is low-pass-filtered:

$$\vec{V}_{dq,fil} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{w_{cU}}} \vec{V}_{dq,meas}$$

The frequency signal is set with a PI-controller:

$$\omega_{meas} = \omega_{ini} + K_{p\omega} V_{q,meas} + K_{i\omega} \frac{1}{s} V_{q,meas}$$

The reference values of active and reactive power are set with a droop control:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{rd} &= -K_{\omega}(\omega_{meas} - \omega_{ref}) + P_{ref} \\ Q_{rd} &= -K_V(|\vec{V}_{dq,fil}| - V_{ref}) + Q_{ref} \end{aligned}$$

Active and reactive power are then adjusted to these reference values with a PI-controller:

$$\begin{aligned} P &= K_{pP}(P_{rd} - P) + K_{iP} \frac{1}{s} (P_{rd} - P) \\ Q &= K_{pQ}(Q_{rd} - Q) + K_{iQ} \frac{1}{s} (Q_{rd} - Q) \end{aligned}$$

The current output is given by the power and the filtered voltage signal:

$$\vec{I}_{dq,out} = \frac{P - jQ}{\vec{V}_{dq,fil}^*}$$

This output can then be transformed back to $\alpha\beta$ -reference-frame:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\theta} &= \omega_{meas} \\ \vec{I}_{\alpha\beta,out} &= e^{j\theta} \vec{I}_{dq,out} \end{aligned}$$

Parameters of the current source inverter

- $w_{cU} = 1.9998/s^{-1}$: Voltage low pass filter cutoff frequency
- $\omega_{ini} = 2\pi \cdot 50$ Hz: PLL initial frequency
- $K_{p\omega} = 2\pi \cdot 0.001 s^{-1}$: Proportional constant of the PLL controller
- $K_{i\omega} = 2\pi \cdot 0.02 s^{-1}$: Integral constant of the PLL controller

- $K_\omega = 2\pi/40000$ Hz/W: P - ω droop constant
- $K_V = 72.914/80000$ V/Var: Q-V droop constant
- V_{ref} : Output voltage reference
- ω_{ref} : Angular frequency reference
- P_{ref} : Active power reference
- Q_{ref} : Reactive power reference
- $K_{pP} = 0.3$: Active power control proportional constant
- $K_{iP} = 1.0$: Active power control integral constant
- $K_{pQ} = 0.3$: Reactive power control proportional constant
- $K_{iQ} = 1.0$: Reactive power control integral constant

4.1.5. Voltage source inverter (grid-forming mode)

The voltage source inverter actively sets voltage and frequency and is therefore also called grid-forming inverter. Basically, the set up consists of a droop control and a low pass filter for the power signal. The mismatch of the actual power and the low-pass-filtered power in the droop control is balanced by an additional power supply. In a real setup this power supply would be a storage element (e.g. a battery). This buffering of the power infeed creates 'virtual' inertia.

Equations of the voltage source inverter The inverter control is implemented in the dq -reference-frame:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{V}_{dq,meas} &= e^{-j\theta} \vec{V}_{\alpha\beta,meas} \\ \vec{I}_{dq,meas} &= e^{-j\theta} \vec{I}_{\alpha\beta,meas}\end{aligned}$$

The measured voltage and current signals are low-pass-filtered:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{V}_{dq,fil} &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{w_{cU}}} \vec{V}_{dq,meas} \\ \vec{I}_{dq,fil} &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{w_{cI}}} \vec{I}_{dq,meas}\end{aligned}$$

From these filtered signals we get the active and reactive power:

$$P_{meas} + jQ_{meas} = \vec{V}_{dq,fil} \vec{I}_{dq,fil}^*$$

The active and reactive powers are controlled by extended low pass filters:

$$P_{fil} = \frac{1 + \frac{s}{n_P \omega_{cP}}}{1 + \frac{s}{\omega_{cP}}} P_{meas}$$

$$Q_{fil} = \frac{1 + \frac{s}{n_Q \omega_{cQ}}}{1 + \frac{s}{\omega_{cQ}}} Q_{meas}$$

Phase angle frequency and voltage amplitude are adjusted to the active and reactive power signals by a droop control:

$$\omega = -K_P(P_{fil} - P_{ref}) + \omega_{ref}$$

$$V = -K_Q(Q_{fil} - Q_{ref}) + V_{ref}$$

The reference frequency and voltage are low pass filtered signals of the set point variables, such that in a abrupt set point dispatch the reference values change smoothly:

$$\omega_{ref} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{\omega_{\omega r}}} \omega_{sp}$$

$$V_{ref} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{\omega_{V r}}} V_{sp}$$

The final voltage output is set by a fictitious impedance:

$$\vec{V}_{dq,out} = V - \vec{I}_{dq,fil} \cdot jX_{fic} - (\vec{I}_{dq,meas} - \vec{I}_{dq,fil})R_{fic}$$

This output can then be transformed back to $\alpha\beta$ -reference-frame:

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega$$

$$\vec{V}_{\alpha\beta,out} = e^{j\theta} \vec{V}_{dq,out}$$

Parameters of the voltage source inverter

- $\omega_{cU} = 198.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$: Voltage low pass filter cutoff frequency
- $\omega_{cI} = 198.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$: Current low pass filter cutoff frequency
- $\omega_{cP} = 0.999 \text{ s}^{-1}$: Active power low pass filter cutoff
- $\omega_{cQ} = 0.999 \text{ s}^{-1}$: Reactive power low pass filter cutoff
- $n_P = 10$: Inverse of the active power low pass filter
- $n_Q = 10$: Inverse of the reactive power low pass filter
- P_{ref} : Active power reference

- Q_{ref} : Reactive power reference
- $\omega_{sp} = 2\pi \cdot 50$ Hz: Angular frequency set point
- $V_{sp} = 0.4$ kV : Voltage amplitude set point
- $K_P = 2\pi/40000$ Hz/W: P - ω droop constant
- $K_Q = 72.914/80000$ V/Var: Q-V droop constant
- $R_{fic} = 0.6\Omega$: Virtual resistance
- $X_{fic} = 0.8\Omega$: Virtual reactance

4.2. Test Cases

Each test case has its own setup which is described in this chapter. For each setup a number of fault scenarios are induced (see chapter 4.3). For a better overview, the setup of the test cases is depicted with a circuit diagram and the parameters are specified in tables.

4.2.1. Test case 1: slack bus and load

In this test case we want to validate our software implementation of static lines and loads by characterizing the dynamic behavior of the components in the lab under different scenarios. Test case 1 can be seen as a baseline testcase for a setup with a slack node, a line and a load. Here, the slack node is a connection to the Spanish grid. Before we build a setup with more complex components like inverters, we study the behaviour of these basic components since they will be present in almost all testcases and thus their modeling builds the basis for all other testcases. The setup is depicted in figure 1 and the parameters used are specified in table 2 and table 3.

Figure 1.: First test case with slack bus, load and a line connecting the two buses

Bus Nr.	Bus Type
1	Slack
2	RLC Load

Table 2.: Buses for test case 1

Line Nr.	Line Type	From Bus	To Bus
1	RL	1	2

Table 3.: Lines for test case 1

4.2.2. Test case 2: slack bus, load and grid-forming inverter

In this test case we want to validate our software implementation of grid-forming inverters by characterizing their dynamic behavior in the lab under different scenarios. In this setup, there is a load and a grid-forming inverter connected to the Spanish grid acting as a slack bus with the focus of studying the behaviour of the grid-forming inverter. Compared to the first test case a grid-forming inverter (with a battery storage system emulated in the background) is added. There are three buses in the system connected by two lines.

Figure 2.: Second test case with slack bus, load, grid-forming inverter and two branches connecting the latter two buses with the slack bus

Bus Nr.	Bus Type
1	Slack
2	RLC Load
3	Grid-forming inverter

Table 4.: Buses for test case 2

Line Nr.	Line Type	From	To
1	RL	1	2
2	π -model	1	3

Table 5.: Lines for test case 2

4.2.3. Test case 2a: Variation of test case 2 without a slack bus

This is the first variation of test case two which is test case 2 without the slack bus (see figure 3) with the corresponding scenarios 2a.2 and 2a.3. Like in testcase 2, there is a load and a grid-forming inverter. However they are not connected to the Spanish grid, thus this is an islanded scenario. The setup consists of a voltage source inverter and a purely resistive load which are connected by a line.

Figure 3.: Test case 2a: Second test case with load and grid-forming inverter in islanded mode.

4.2.4. Test case 2b: Variation of test case 2 with a different line connection

This is the second variation of test case 2 with a different line connection (see figure 4) with the corresponding scenarios 2b.2b, 2b.3 and 2.4b.

Figure 4.: Test case 2b: Second test case with slack bus, load, grid-forming inverter and two lines connecting the latter two buses with the slack bus

4.2.5. Test case 3b: slack bus, load, grid-forming inverter and grid-following inverter with solar plant

In this test case we want to validate our software implementation of grid-following inverters and their dynamic interaction with grid-forming inverters in the lab under different fault scenarios. There is an RLC load, a grid-forming inverter and a grid-following inverter in the setup.

Bus Nr.	Bus Type
1	Slack
2	RLC Load
3	Grid-forming inverter
4	Grid-following inverter

Table 6.: Buses for test case 3

Figure 5.: Test case 3b with slack bus, load, grid-forming inverter, grid-following inverter with a solar plant, and three lines connecting the latter three buses with the slack bus

Line Nr.	Line Type	From Bus	To Bus
1	RL	1	2
2	π -model	1	3
3	π -model	1	4

Table 7.: Lines for test case 3

4.2.6. Test case 5: pacific power source, load and grid-forming inverter

In this test case we want to validate our software implementation of the grid-forming inverter by investigating the setup of a grid-forming inverter with a pacific power source and load in the lab under different fault scenarios. In the setup, there is a pacific power source, a RLC load as well as a grid-forming inverter.

Figure 6.: Fifth test case with pacific power source, a load and a grid-forming inverter, and three lines connecting the latter three buses with the pacific power source

Bus Nr.	Bus Type
1	Power source
2	RLC Load
3	Grid-forming inverter

Table 8.: Buses for test case 5

Line Nr.	Line Type	From Bus	To Bus
1	RL	1	2
2	π -model	1	3

Table 9.: Lines for test case 5

4.2.7. Test case 6: pacific power source, load and grid-following inverter

In this test case we want to validate our software implementation of the grid-following inverter by investigating the setup of a grid-following inverter with a pacific power source and load in the lab under different fault scenarios. The components in this setup are a pacific power source, a RLC load and a grid-following inverter.

Figure 7.: Sixth test case with pacific power source, a load and a grid-following inverter, and three lines connecting the latter three buses with the pacific power source

Bus Nr.	Bus Type
1	Power source
2	RLC Load
3	Grid-following inverter

Table 10.: Buses for test case 6

Line Nr.	Line Type	From Bus	To Bus
1	RL	1	2
2	π -model	1	3

Table 11.: Lines for test case 6

4.3. Fault Scenarios

For each of the test cases above, a number of fault scenarios has been performed to monitor the behaviour of the components. In fault scenario tables the scenario title, test design, target measures and temporal resolution are documented. In the parameter tables, the parameters for different setup variations within the scenario are shown. The results are plotted in per units (pu) with a base voltage of 400 V, a base active power of 10 kW and a base reactive power of 10 kVar.

Scenario 1.1

Title	Active power load drop
Reference test case	Test case 1
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 13 and table 14 2. the active power consumption at the load is suddenly reduced to 11.11 kW 3. change back the active power consumption at the load to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Table 12.: Fault scenario 1: Active power load drop

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0

Table 13.: Bus parameters for scenario 1.1

Line Type	R [Ω]	L [mH]
RL	0.25	0.98

Table 14.: Line parameters for scenario 1.1

For scenario 1.1 the load consists of an ohmic resistance without reactance (see figure 1). The fault scenario was a sudden drop in the active power consumption of the load which is changed back to the original value after a certain time. As expected, figure 8 shows that the slack reacts instantaneously in compensating the change of active power while its frequency and voltage remain unaffected. For the load, however, the change in active power consumption results in a sudden step of the voltage amplitude.

Figure 8.: Results for Scenario 1.1

Scenario 1.3

Title	Active power load drop
Reference test case	Test case 1
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 16 and table 17 2. the active power consumption at the load is suddenly reduced to 11.11 kW 3. change back the active power consumption at the load to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Table 15.: Fault scenario 1: Active power load drop

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0

Table 16.: Bus parameters for scenario 1.3

Line Type	R [Ω]	L [mH]
RL	0.05	0.98

Table 17.: Line parameters for scenario 1.3

Scenario 1.3 is similar to scenario 1.1 (see figure 1), the only difference being a lower line resistance. In scenario 1.3 the line resistance is changed from the 0.25Ω in scenario 1.1 to 0.05Ω . Comparing figures 8 and 9, it can be seen that the lower line resistance results in less pronounced frequency peaks and voltage change at the load due to smaller ohmic losses.

Figure 9.: Results for Scenario 1.3

Scenario 1.5

Title	Reactive power load increase
Reference test case	Test case 1
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 18 and 19 2. the reactive power consumption at the load is suddenly increased to 10 kVar 3. change back the reactive power consumption at the load back to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0

Table 18.: Bus parameters for scenario 1.5

Line Type	R [Ω]	L [mH]
RL	0.05	0.98

Table 19.: Line parameters for scenario 1.5

Scenario 1.5 has a similar setup to scenario 1.1. (see figure 1). The only difference in the setup is that the load has now a reactive part as well. The fault scenario is now an increase of the reactive power consumption at the load while the active power is fixed. Figure 10 shows that in this case the voltage at the load decreases when the reactive power consumption increases. We also note that there is a significant frequency peak at the load and an overshoot of reactive as well as active power when the reactive power consumption is increased.

Figure 10.: Results for Scenario 1.5

Scenario 2a.2

Title	Large Load Increase
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2a
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 20 and table 21 2. the active power consumption at the load is suddenly increased to 37.4 kW 3. change back the active power consumption at the load to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
RLC Load	0	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 20.: Bus parameters for scenario 2a.2

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.05	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 21.: Line parameters for scenario 2a.2

Test case 2a is a variation of test case 2 in that the slack is disconnected and thus represents an islanded scenario where power imbalances are not compensated (see figure 3 for the setup and table 4.3 for details on the fault scenario). It can be seen in figure 11 that, as the active power in-feed of the inverter is set at 20 kW while the active power consumption at the load is zero at the beginning, the frequency starts out above 50 Hz and then slowly decreases after the active power consumption at the load is increased reaching a steady state below 50 Hz. Due to the large and sudden increase of active power there are also significant frequency and voltage spikes at the load.

Figure 11.: Results for Scenario 2a.2

Scenario 2b.2

Title	Large Load Increase
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 22 and table 23 2. the active power consumption at the load is suddenly increased to 37.4 kW 3. change back the active power consumption at the load to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	0	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 22.: Bus parameters for scenario 2b.2

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.05	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 23.: Line parameters for scenario 2b.2

For test case 2b the line resistance at the load in test case 2 is placed at the slack so that the inverter is affected by changes at the load (see figure 4). In the beginning of the experiment, the power consumption at the load is zero and the grid balances the power that the inverter is feeding into the system. The fault scenario is an increase of active power consumption at the load just as in the previous scenario (see 4.3) but now the power imbalance is compensated and the frequency therefore remains at 50 Hz, as seen in figure 12. We observe active power overshoots at the inverter, a voltage step for both the inverter and the load, and further a slight increase of reactive power consumption at the load.

Figure 12.: Results for Scenario 2b.2

Scenario 2.3

Title	Power set point dispatch
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 24 and 25 2. decrease the active power set point of the inverter by applying a change to the frequency set point by -0.25 s^{-1} 3. change back the frequency set point of the inverter to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 24.: Bus parameters for scenario 2.3

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 25.: Line parameters for scenario 2.3

Scenario 2.3 is an active power set point dispatch at the inverter (for the setup see figure 2). Although for technical reasons this is realized by a change in the frequency set point which results in the same steady state but has a slightly different transient because of the low pass filter applied to the frequency set point. It can be seen in Figure 13 that frequencies and voltages are unaffected by the dispatch while the transients of active and reactive power at the inverter (and of course at the slack which mirrors the inverter) show small overshoots. As the slack balances the power, its active power changes sign since the system changes from a net surplus to a net deficiency of active power.

Figure 13.: Results for Scenario 2.3

Scenario 2a.3

Title	Power set point dispatch
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2a
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 26 and 27 2. decrease the active power set point of the inverter by applying a change to the frequency set point by -0.25 s^{-1} 3. change back the frequency set point of the inverter to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
RLC Load	16.67	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 26.: Bus parameters for scenario 2a.3

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 27.: Line parameters for scenario 2a.3

In scenario 2a.3 the same power set point dispatch is applied to the inverter as in scenario 2.3 but this time the system operates in islanded mode (for the setup see figure 3). Therefore, the active power in-feed of the inverter is determined by the active power consumption at the load and instead of a change in active power we observe a change in frequency, see figure 14. At the beginning the active power in-feed of the inverter is below its set point and the resulting frequency is above 50 Hz. After the dispatch the in-feed is above its set point and the resulting frequency is below 50 Hz.

Figure 14.: Results for Scenario 2a.3

Scenario 2b.3

Title	Power set point dispatch
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 28 and 29 2. decrease the active power set point of the inverter by applying a change to the frequency set point by -0.25 s^{-1} 3. change back the frequency set point of the inverter to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 28.: Bus parameters for scenario 2b.3

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 29.: Line parameters for scenario 2b.3

In scenario 2b.3 again the same set point dispatch is applied but with the test case as depicted in figure 4. Comparing figure 15 for this scenario to figure 13 for scenario 2.3, it can be seen that in addition to the transients of active and reactive power there are also overshoots at the voltage of load and inverter. Further to note is the non-zero reactive power consumption at the load which has not been observed for scenario 2.3.

Figure 15.: Results for Scenario 2b.3

Scenario 2b.4

Title	Line fault (Line opening and Line closing)
Reference Test Case	Test Case 2b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 30 and 31 2. remove the line connecting the load with the rest of the system 3. reconnect the load 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms.

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 30.: Bus parameters for scenario 2b.4

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 31.: Line parameters for scenario 2b.4

In scenario 2b.4 the system is disconnected from the slack operating in islanding mode for a while and is then reconnected to the slack (see figure 4). As the system is disconnected from the slack, the inverter has to balance the power in the system and the frequency rises above 50 Hz which can be seen in figure 16. When the system is reconnected to the slack it returns to its original state after a short transient with overshoots at active and reactive power as well as voltage.

Figure 16.: Results for Scenario 2b.4

Scenario 3b.2

Title	Large Load Increase
Reference Test Case	Test Case 3b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 32 and table 33 2. the active power consumption at the load is suddenly increased to 37.4 kW 3. change back the active power consumption at the load to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	0	0
Voltage source inverter	20	0
Current source inverter	20	0

Table 32.: Bus parameters for scenario 3b.2

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.05	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 33.: Line parameters for scenario 3b.2

In scenario 3b.2 the setup consists of a load, a voltage source inverter (VSI) and a current source inverter (CSI) which are connected to the Spanish grid acting as the slack bus (see figure 5). The fault scenario is a large and sudden increase of active power consumption at the load. It can be seen in figure 17 that the active power both at the current and the voltage source inverter is unaffected (they are both feeding in at their respective power set points) as the slack bus balances the change in active power but their noise level noticeably decreases. However, the reactive power in-feeds change at both inverters with a significant transient for the current source inverter. Further, there is a change of the voltage at both inverters and at the load.

Figure 17.: Results for Scenario 3b.2

Scenario 3b.4

Title	Power set point dispatch
Reference Test Case	Test Case 3b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 34 and 35 2. decrease the active power set point of the current source inverter by applying a change to the frequency set point by -0.25 s^{-1} 3. change back the frequency set point of the current source inverter to the initial value 4. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0
Voltage source inverter	20	0
Current source inverter	20	0

Table 34.: Bus parameters for scenario 3b.4

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 35.: Line parameters for scenario 3b.4

Scenario 3b.4 is a dispatch of the active power set point at the current source inverter (see figure 5 for the setup). Comparing figure 18 to figure 15 from scenario 2b.3, it can be seen that the transients at the current source inverter for both the active and reactive power are qualitatively different in that they are much longer but do not feature overshoots in this scenario. Additionally, there is a change of voltage at all nodes except the slack.

Figure 18.: Results for Scenario 3b.4

Scenario 3b.5

Title	Line fault (Line opening)
Reference Test Case	Test Case 3b
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 36 and 37 2. remove the line connecting the load with the rest of the system 3. stop the experiment
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms.

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	16.67	0
Voltage source inverter	20	0
Current source inverter	10	0

Table 36.: Bus parameters for scenario 3b.5

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.25	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.98$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 37.: Line parameters for scenario 3b.5

In this scenario the system is disconnected from the slack bringing it into islanded mode (for the setup see figure 5). In the beginning, as the system is still connected, the slack balances the active power and the two inverters feed in at their respective power set points. When the connection to the slack is lost the inverters have to balance the power consumption of the load. In order to avoid tripping of the inverters, the current source inverter now has an active power set point of only 10 kW. Figure 19 shows that the transients at the voltage source inverter feature sharp changes with overshoots while for the current source inverter the changes are smooth.

Figure 19.: Results for Scenario 3b.5

Scenario 5.1

Title	Frequency ramps up and down
Reference Test Case	Test Case 5
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 38 and table 39 2. the frequency at the pacific power source is stepping up and back down again several times with ramps of decreasing slopes
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	29.17	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 38.: Bus parameters for scenarios 5.1x

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.11	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.67$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 39.: Line parameters for scenarios 5.1x

Scenario	τ_p	K_p
5.11	τ_{p0}	K_{p0}
5.12	τ_{p0}	$2K_{p0}$
5.13	τ_{p0}	$4K_{p0}$
5.14	$\tau_{p0}/4$	K_{p0}
5.15	$\tau_{p0}/2$	K_{p0}

Table 40.: Parameters for test case 5, scenarios 5.1x, $K_{p0} = 2\pi \cdot 1/40000$ Hz/W, $\tau_{p0} = 1.001$ s

In this testcase, the slack is now a pacific power source (see section 4.1.2). It behaves like a slack as long as it is feeding power into the system. To ensure that the nature

of the pacific power source is a slack, it is ensured that the load in the system has a power consumption which is larger than the set point of the inverter. This inverter is operating in voltage source mode. In scenarios 5.1x, the frequency at the slack bus is changed several times with decreasing slopes (meaning that the change in frequency is less and less sudden). The difference between the scenarios is the variations in the parameters τ_p and K_p as shown in table 40. These scenarios are not meant to be realistic fault scenarios but should reveal the dynamic behaviour of the inverter. As the system operates at 50Hz, the active power at the inverter is at its setpoint. When the frequency at the slack changes, the inverter has to adjust its active power in-feed. Figure 20 shows similar transients as for the power set point dispatch (figure 15) where the overshoots decrease as the changes become less sudden (the result figures for scenarios 5.12-5.15 can be found in appendix B).

Figure 20.: Results for Scenario 5.11

Scenario 5.2

Title	Voltage drop and recovery
Reference Test Case	Test Case 5
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 41 and 42 2. the voltage at the pacific power source is stepping down and back up again with increasing step size
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	29.17	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 41.: Bus parameters for scenarios 5.2x

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.11	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.67$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 42.: Line parameters for scenarios 5.2x

Scenario	τ_Q	K_Q
5.21	τ_{Q0}	K_{Q0}
5.22	τ_{Q0}	$K_{Q0}/2$
5.23	τ_{Q0}	$2K_{Q0}$
5.24	$\tau_{Q0}/2$	K_{Q0}
5.25	$\tau_{Q0}/4$	K_{Q0}

Table 43.: Parameters for test case 5, scenario 5.2x, $K_{Q0} = 72.914/80000$ V/Var, $\tau_{Q0} = 1.001$ s

In the scenarios 5.2x (5.21-5.25), the voltage amplitude at the slack (the pacific power source) is changed abruptly (for the setup see section 4.2.6). The scenarios differ in

the parameters τ_Q and K_Q as depicted in table 43. As shown in figure 21, we can now observe transients at the reactive power with significant overshoots and peaks at the active power of the inverter. The frequency remains unaffected. In every scenario, voltage steps of different height are induced by the pacific power source. It can be observed that larger steps in voltage lead to more pronounced overshoots (the result figures for scenarios 5.22-5.25 can be found in appendix B).

Figure 21.: Results for Scenario 5.21

Scenario 6.1

Title	Frequency ramps up and down
Reference Test Case	Test Case 6
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 44 and table 45 2. the frequency at the pacific power source is stepping up and back down again several times with ramps of decreasing slopes
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	29.17	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 44.: Bus parameters for scenarios 6.1x

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.11	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.67$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 45.: Line parameters for scenarios 6.1x

Scenario	$K_{P\omega}$	$K_{I\omega}$	K_P
6.11	$K_{P\omega 0}$	$K_{I\omega 0}$	K_{P0}
6.12	$K_{P\omega 0}$	$K_{I\omega 0}$	$2K_{P0}$
6.13	$K_{P\omega 0}$	$K_{I\omega 0}$	$4K_{P0}$
6.14	$2K_{P\omega 0}$	$2K_{I\omega 0}$	K_{P0}
6.15	$K_{P\omega 0}/2$	$K_{I\omega 0}/2$	K_{P0}

Table 46.: Parameters for test case 6, scenarios 6.1x, $K_{P\omega 0} = 2\pi \cdot 0.001$, $K_{I\omega 0} = 2\pi \cdot 0.02$, $K_{P0} = 2\pi \cdot 1/40000$

In test case 6, the setup is similar to test case 5 but the inverter is operating in current source mode (see section 4.2.7 for the setup). In the scenarios 6.1x, the frequency is

changed at the slack with different slopes. The scenarios differ with regard to the parameters $K_{P\omega}$, $K_{I\omega}$ and K_P . Comparing figure 22 to figure 20 of scenarios 5.11 which has the same setup but with a voltage source inverter instead of the current source inverter in this scenario, the transients are smoother without overshoots (the result figures for scenarios 6.12-6.15 can be found in appendix C).

Figure 22.: Results for Scenario 6.11

Scenario 6.2

Title	Voltage drop and recovery
Reference Test Case	Test Case 6
Test design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. start system at the operation point that is determined by the parameters in table 47 and 48 2. the voltage at the pacific power source is stepping down and back up again with increasing step size
Target measures	3-phase voltage and current for all objects of investigation
Temporal resolution	1ms

Bus	P [kW]	Q [kVar]
Slack	-	-
RLC Load	29.17	0
Inverter	20	0

Table 47.: Bus parameters for scenarios 6.2x

Line Type	R [Ω]	X [m Ω]	R_{shunt} [Ω]	X_{shunt} [Ω]
RL	0.11	$2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot 0.67$	-	-
π -model	0.0474	64.5	536.88	125.26

Table 48.: Line parameters for scenarios 6.2x

Scenario	ω_{cU}	K_Q
6.21	ω_{cU0}	K_{Q0}
6.22	ω_{cU0}	$K_{Q0}/2$
6.23	ω_{cU0}	$2K_{Q0}$
6.24	$\omega_{cU0}/2$	K_{Q0}
6.25	$2\omega_{cU0}$	K_{Q0}

Table 49.: Parameters for test case 6, scenario 6.2x, $\omega_{cU0} = 1.9998 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $K_{Q0} = 72.914/80000 \text{ V/Var}$

The scenarios 6.2x are the same as 5.2x but with the inverter in current source mode (see section 4.2.7 for the setup). Figure 23 shows significant overshoots at the voltages at

both the inverter and the load. While the active power in-feed of the inverter is affected very little, the reactive power in-feed shows drastic changes as the voltage steps become larger (the result figures for scenarios 6.22-6.25 can be found in appendix C).

Figure 23.: Results for Scenario 6.21

5. Data Processing and Numerical Simulations

5.1. Post-processing of measurement data

The data for the slack and the load comprise the three phases of the voltage (u_a, u_b, u_c) and the current (i_a, i_b, i_c) which are measured line to neutral (star connection). We group them into the vectors

$$u_{abc} = (u_a, u_b, u_c)^T, \quad i_{abc} = (i_a, i_b, i_c)^T.$$

For the inverters (delta connection) the voltages are measured line to line (u_{ab}, u_{bc}, u_{ca}) such that an additional factor of $\sqrt{3}$ is necessary and further a factor $\alpha = 0.92008$ is accounting for the transformer. The vector of the three phase voltage at the inverters is thus given by

$$u_{abc} = \frac{1}{\alpha \sqrt{3}} (u_{ab}, u_{bc}, u_{ca})^T.$$

The next step is to change the frame of reference to the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ frame according to

$$u_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = T u_{abc}, \quad i_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = T i_{abc},$$

with the transformation matrix T defined as

$$T = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1/2 & -1/2 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3}/2 & -\sqrt{3}/2 \\ 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Care has to be taken that the order of the phases is correct when grouping them into vectors because only then the respective third components u_γ and i_γ are zero such that we can henceforth work with only two phases. We further remark that this version of the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ transformation leaves the power invariant but increases the amplitude of voltage and current by a factor of $\sqrt{3}/2$. The complex phasors u and i can now be constructed as $u = u_\alpha + j u_\beta$ and $i = i_\alpha + j i_\beta$ with the imaginary unit j .

As the raw measurement data is too noisy to allow for an immediate calculation of our target measures, an average over one period has to be taken. To this end we first transform to the rotary frame of reference (dq-frame) by

$$u_{rot} = u e^{-2\pi j f_0 t}, \quad i_{rot} = i e^{-2\pi j f_0 t},$$

with the nominal frequency f_0 . For the scenarios with a slack bus we have $f_0 = 50$ Hz but depending on the measurement setup one might have to use a negative frequency for the transformation to the rotary frame of reference as voltage and current may appear to rotate clockwise or counterclockwise in general. If the scenario features no slack bus (island scenario) or is otherwise expected to have a different nominal frequency one can use a Fourier transformation on one of the phases of voltage or current and take the dominant mode as an estimate for f_0 . Having thus eliminated the fundamental oscillations an average over one period can be computed as

$$\bar{u}_{rot}(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_t^{t+T} u_{rot}(t') dt' , \quad \bar{i}_{rot}(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_t^{t+T} i_{rot}(t') dt'$$

with $T = 1/f_0$ and from this our target measures are calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \Re(\bar{u}_{rot} \bar{i}_{rot}^*) , \\ Q &= \Im(\bar{u}_{rot} \bar{i}_{rot}^*) , \\ V &= |\bar{u}_{rot}| , \\ \omega &= \frac{d}{dt} \arg \bar{u}_{rot} . \end{aligned}$$

Remark: Before numerically differentiating the angle $\theta = \arg \bar{u}_{rot}$ it must be ensured that there are no discontinuities (jumps by 2π) when using some inbuilt argument function.

5.2. Dynamic Modelling

When implementing a time-domain simulation of the dynamics we basically have to transform the inverter equations in section 4.1.4 and 4.1.5 from Laplace into time space. For the voltage source inverter, combining the droop control and the extended low pass filter of the measured power leads to the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\theta} &= \omega(t) \\ \dot{\omega} &= \frac{1}{\tau_P} [\omega_{sp} - \omega(t)] + \frac{K_P}{\tau_P} [P_{ref} - P_{meas}(t)] - \frac{K_P}{n_P} \dot{P}_{meas}(t) \\ \dot{V} &= \frac{1}{\tau_Q} [V_{sp} - V(t)] + \frac{K_Q}{\tau_Q} [Q_{ref} - Q_{meas}(t)] - \frac{k_Q}{n_Q} \dot{Q}_{meas}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Here we introduced the time constants $\tau_P = 1/\omega_{cP} = 1/\omega_{or}$ and $\tau_Q = 1/\omega_{cQ} = 1/\omega_{vr}$. For the PLL of the current source inverter the dynamic equation is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{V}_{dq,meas} &= e^{-j\theta} \underline{V}_{\alpha\beta,meas} \\ \dot{\theta} &= \omega_{ini} + K_{p\omega} V_{q,meas} + K_{i\omega} \int_0^t V_{q,meas}(t') dt' \end{aligned}$$

In our simulation software *PowerDynamics.jl* there exists a user interface in form of a macro¹ that allows for custom built dynamic node types. We implemented the two inverter types with the help of this macro (see Appendix A). The lines and transformers are implemented as static elements and the loads as a algebraic constraint consuming a fixed amount of power. Further, we had to implement a connector line and a connector node in order to achieve the star-like connection set up (see Fig. 4). For testing the simulations we have chosen the scenarios 2b.2 and 2b.3. The results are depicted in Fig. 24 and Fig. 25.

Figure 24.: Simulation for Scenario 2b.2 with CSI (green), load (red), slack (blue) and connector node (purple).

Scenario 2b.2 is a large increase of the resistive load. We see that the simulation results of frequency and active power are consistent with the measurement. Both frequency and active power of the inverter remains unaffected since the slack completely balances the change in active power consumption. However, for voltage amplitude and reactive power we see significant deviations from the measurement results. The voltage amplitude of the load steps down as in the measurement but the voltage of the inverter remains unaffected. Even more severe are the deviations of simulation and measurement in the reactive power. At the operation point the reactive power of the

¹https://juliaenergy.github.io/PowerDynamics.jl/stable/custom_node_types/

inverter has a different sign and is completely unaffected by the load increase in the simulations in contrast to the measurement. Our conjecture is that the cause of the deviations between measurement and simulation is our very simplified model of the load. In the simulation it is modelled as a simple algebraic constraint that fixes the amount of power, whereas in the experiment we changed the resistance of the load which also affects the voltage amplitude in the system.

Figure 25.: Simulation for Scenario 2b.3 with CSI (green), load (red), slack (blue) and connector node (purple).

Scenario 2b.3 is a power set point dispatch of the inverter. As in the previous case, the simulation of frequency and active power are consistent with the measurement but there were severe deviations regarding voltage amplitude and reactive power. Again, there is a mismatch for the reactive power at the operation point. This time the reactive power of the inverter is affected by the change of the setpoint, but the change does not match quantitatively. We think the reason for this deviations is as in the previous scenario the oversimplified model of the load. However, we also do not see the dynamic overshoots in the simulation that are clearly visible in the measurement. Since we do not know what the cause of this dynamic phenomenon is, it is hard to determine whether the lack of this effect in the simulations is caused by an inaccurate parametrization of the inverter or the non-dynamic models of load and lines. Further investigation is needed here.

6. Conclusions and Outlook

With the measurements at the smart grid laboratory at Technalia we aimed to test the practical usability of our software package *PowerDynamics.jl* in general but also to validate the implemented models of various components as well as fault scenarios. A specific focus was the implementation of control schemes of different inverter types. The software contains a node macro which makes it very convenient for users to implement the dynamic equations of an inverter without having to deal with the details and challenges of operation point search and numerical integration of a large dynamical system. On this specific manner, we are quite satisfied with the current state of our software. Once the equations and exact parametrization were clarified, it took only a few lines of code to implement the control schemes of Tecnalias custom built current source and voltage source inverter (see appendix A). However, some detail, e.g. the implementation of the fictitious impedance in the voltage source inverter, turned out to be rather intricate to implement with the current design of the node macro. Here, minor adjustments in the software may be necessary.

A major issue that occurred in the analysis of the measurement data as well as in the modelling was the question of (frequency) reference frames, especially in case of islanded scenarios. This issue will force us to rethink some software design decisions on a broader scale. For our simulations in *PowerDynamics.jl* we assume the system to be in the co-rotating or dq -frame of the reference frequency (e.g. 50Hz). However, in an islanded scenario where the net power consumption does not match with the power set points of the grid-forming inverters, the droop control has to set up a slight mismatch between the operation grid frequency and the reference frequency in order to establish power balance in the grid. However, if the grid frequency is different from the reference frequency the software is at the moment not able to find the valid operation point of the system. We will have to investigate how to solve this problem and which design changes are necessary.

Another issue we had, was that *PowerDynamics.jl* at the moment only allows for connecting one single dynamical component to a bus. We therefore had to implement simple connector nodes and lines in order to set up the simulations for certain test cases. However, the current solution seems to be numerically unstable in some specific situations and we therefore need to develop a more robust solution for this problem in the future.

In the preparation of this project and during our stay in the lab we mainly focused on the exact modelling of the inverter dynamics and did not spend much time to accurately

model other components as lines, loads and transformers. However, in the evaluation of the measurements and simulations we realised that the modelling of these components might have a larger impact on the outcome of the different fault scenarios than we originally expected. At the moment, both lines and loads are implemented as simple algebraic constraints in *PowerDynamics.jl*. On one hand, a large number of such algebraic constraints can lead to problems with the numerical integration. On the other hand we realised that for certain fault scenarios the behavior of absolute voltage and reactive power heavily depend on the specific model of the load. We therefore decided to invest more time in extending our library of implemented load and line models in the nearer future.

In conclusion we hope to address most of the aforementioned issues in the next major release of *PowerDynamics.jl*, in order to make the software even more useful and convenient, not only in the context of theoretical research but also for practical applications as the dynamical stability analysis of inverter-based microgrids.

7. References

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A. Julia Code for Inverter Models

```
1 @DynamicNode GridFormingTecnalia(omega_r,tau_U, tau_I, tau_V, tau_omega,  
   tau_P, tau_Q, n_P, n_Q, K_P, K_Q, P, Q, V_r, R_f, X_f) begin  
2   MassMatrix(m_u = true, m_int = [true,true,true,true,true])  
3 end begin  
4   @assert tau_U >= 0  
5   @assert tau_I >= 0  
6   @assert tau_P >= 0  
7   @assert tau_Q >= 0  
8   @assert n_P >= 0  
9   @assert n_Q >= 0  
10  @assert K_P >= 0  
11  @assert K_Q >= 0  
12  @assert V_r >= 0  
13  @assert R_f >= 0  
14  @assert X_f >= 0  
15 end [[u_fil_r,du_fil_r],[u_fil_i,du_fil_i],[i_fil_r,di_fil_r],[i_fil_i,  
   di_fil_i],[omega, domega]] begin  
16  
17   du_fil_r = 1/tau_U*(-u_fil_r + real(u))  
18   du_fil_i = 1/tau_U*(-u_fil_i + imag(u))  
19  
20   di_fil_r = 1/tau_I*(-i_fil_r + real(i))  
21   di_fil_i = 1/tau_I*(-i_fil_i + imag(i))  
22  
23   u_fil = u_fil_r +1im*u_fil_i  
24   i_fil = i_fil_r +1im*i_fil_i  
25  
26   p = real(u_fil * conj(i_fil))  
27   dp = du_fil_r*i_fil_r+u_fil_r*di_fil_r+du_fil_i*i_fil_i+du_fil_i*  
   di_fil_i  
28  
29   q = imag(u_fil * conj(i_fil))  
30   dq = -du_fil_r*i_fil_i-u_fil_r*di_fil_i+du_fil_i*i_fil_r+u_fil_i*  
   di_fil_r  
31  
32   domega = 1/tau_P*(omega_r-omega) + K_P/tau_P*(P-p) - K_P/n_P*dp  
33   v = abs(u_fil)  
34   dv = 1/tau_Q*(V_r-v) + K_Q/tau_Q*(Q-q) - K_Q/n_Q*dq  
35   du = u*1im*(omega-omega_r)+dv*(u/v)  
36 end  
37
```

```
38 export GridFormingTecnalia

1  @DynamicNode GridFollowingTecnalia(tau_u,omega_ini,K_pomega,K_iomega,K_omega
   ,K_v,omega_r,V_r,P,Q_r) begin
2    MassMatrix(m_u = false, m_int = [true,true,true,true])
3  end begin
4    @assert tau_u >= 0
5    @assert omega_ini >= 0
6    @assert K_pomega >= 0
7    @assert K_iomega >= 0
8    @assert K_omega >= 0
9    @assert K_v >= 0
10 end [[u_fil_d,du_fil_d],[u_fil_q,du_fil_q],[e_Iomega,de_Iomega],[theta,
    dtheta]] begin
11
12   u_dq = exp(-im*theta)*u
13   u_q = imag(u_dq)
14   du_fil_d = 1/tau_u*(-u_fil_d + real(u_dq))
15   du_fil_q = 1/tau_u*(-u_fil_q + imag(u_dq))
16   u_fil_dq = u_fil_d + im*u_fil_q
17
18   e_omega = -u_q
19   de_Iomega= e_omega
20   omega = omega_ini - K_pomega*e_omega - K_iomega*e_Iomega
21   dtheta = omega
22
23   p = -K_omega*(omega-omega_r) + P
24   q = -K_v*(abs(u_fil_dq)-V_r) + Q_r
25   i_fil_dq = (p-im*q)/u_fil_dq
26   du = i - i_fil_dq*exp(im*theta)
27 end
28
29 export GridFollowingTecnalia
```

B. Result Tables Scenarios 5.x

Figure 26.: Results for Scenario 5.12

Figure 27.: Results for Scenario 5.13

Figure 28.: Results for Scenario 5.14

Figure 29.: Results for Scenario 5.15

Figure 30.: Results for Scenario 5.22

Figure 31.: Results for Scenario 5.23

Figure 32.: Results for Scenario 5.24

Figure 33.: Results for Scenario 5.25

C. Result Tables Scenarios 6.x

Figure 34.: Results for Scenario 6.12

Figure 35.: Results for Scenario 6.13

Figure 36.: Results for Scenario 6.14

Figure 37.: Results for Scenario 6.15

Figure 38.: Results for Scenario 6.22

Figure 39.: Results for Scenario 6.23

Figure 40.: Results for Scenario 6.24

Figure 41.: Results for Scenario 6.25